

**THE TRANSFER OF THE SECOND WORLD WAR TO THE SOVIET UNION
TERRITORY AND THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE IN THE WAR
WHIRLPOOL**

Ismoilova Feruza Ibragimovna
Teacher, Asian University of Technologies

Abstract: The years of the Second World War in Uzbekistan are distinguished by complex and contradictory events. During the war, all sectors in Soviet Uzbekistan were directed toward meeting the needs of the front. Within a short period, industry was adapted to wartime conditions. Industrial enterprises, scientific institutions, and the population were evacuated from the West to various parts of Uzbekistan. People of all social strata were mobilized for labor. Women, the elderly, and children took the places of men who went to war. These processes unfolded uniquely in every region of Uzbekistan. Therefore, studying these events from a modern perspective remains a crucial task for historians. This was emphasized in the President's speech during the May 9, 2020, celebration of the 75th anniversary of victory and the "Remembrance and Honor" Day.

Keywords: Women, industrial enterprises, activity, agriculture, production, grain growing, evacuation, raw materials, blacksmiths, workshops.

Introduction

This dissertation serves, to a certain extent, in the implementation of the tasks outlined in the following normative-legal documents:

- Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4495 dated October 23, 2019, "On the Proper Celebration of the 75th Anniversary of Victory in the Second World War";
- Presidential Decree No. PF-6209 dated April 20, 2021, "On the Encouragement of Second World War Participants";
- Presidential Decree No. PF-6224 dated May 11, 2021, "On Measures to Further Strengthen the Material Support for Participants of the Second World War";
- Presidential Decree No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026";
- Presidential Decree No. PQ-229 dated April 29, 2022, "On Measures for the Preparation and Celebration of May 9 – the Day of Remembrance and Honor," along with other normative and legal documents in the field.

In addition, these documents raise issues such as mobilizing the people of Uzbekistan against fascism and strengthening the front with support from the home front.

In the years of independence, the study of the history of the Second World War has remained one of the most pressing issues. During this period, scholarly works and research have been produced by X. Ibragimov, B. Salimbetov, D.M. Li, and others. These studies have objectively covered issues such as the socio-economic conditions of the Uzbek people during the war years.

Among the studies related to the history of the Qashqadarya oasis during the Second World War, the research of Sattor Turdiyev and Nodira Irkayeva is particularly noteworthy. These works describe the lives of Qashqadarya residents during the war years, the socio-economic situation of the region, the population's contributions to the front, issues surrounding the resettlement of evacuees, the militarization of industry and agriculture, as well as matters of education and culture.

After the significant losses suffered during the periods of collectivization and dekulakization, as well as mass political repression, by the late 1930s and early 1940s, the population of Uzbekistan gradually began to recover under a temporary period of peace and engaged in active constructive activity. During this period, the appearance of Uzbek villages and cities began to change.

On January 15, 1938, the Uzbek SSR was divided into its first five administrative regions: Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana, and Khorezm. On March 6, 1941, Surkhandarya region was separated from the Bukhara region, and the Andijan and Namangan regions were separated from the Fergana region. Many new districts and cities were established in Uzbekistan, and the number of village councils increased.

In Uzbekistan, the further advancement of cotton and other branches of agriculture was closely connected with the resolution of water supply problems. Ensuring irrigation of fertile lands in the Fergana and Zarafshan valleys, the Khorezm oasis, and the Mirzachul region was a top priority.

In July 1939, the Plenum of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) considered the issue of constructing the Great Fergana Canal. It approved the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of People's Commissars of the Uzbek SSR, dated June 6, 1939, on practical measures for canal construction. It assigned party and Soviet organizations the responsibility of conducting

extensive public outreach among collective farmers and laborers about the importance of the canal and providing practical assistance in its construction.

During this period in Uzbekistan, the method of public construction through voluntary labor (hashar) became widespread. Using this method, in addition to the Great Fergana Canal, the Northern and Southern Fergana canals, the Toshsoqa Canal in Khorezm, the Kampirravot Dam, the large canal named after V.I. Lenin in Karakalpakstan, and the Tashkent Canal and other irrigation facilities were built. Also, the Kattakurgan Reservoir began to be constructed, although it was completed after the war.

At a time when public construction was flourishing and the Uzbek people were actively engaged in creative labor, major geopolitical changes were taking place. On August 23, 1939, the USSR and Germany signed a non-aggression pact for a term of ten years (known historically as the Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact). In its secret protocol, the two countries delineated their future borders and spheres of influence. Soviet influence expanded over Poland, the Baltic States, and Finland.

World War II began on September 1, 1939, when Nazi Germany attacked Poland. On September 3, France and the United Kingdom declared war on Germany. On September 17, under the secret terms of the non-aggression pact, Soviet troops invaded Poland. The division of Poland began. On September 19, the Red Army occupied Vilnius.

At that time, Uzbekistan had 352 mills, 408 oil presses, 66 blacksmith shops, and 36 workshops. However, the working conditions in Kashkadarya, as in the rest of the republic, did not significantly improve by 1943 or in subsequent years. There was a continued shortage of raw materials and electricity necessary for military production.

Idle factories and poor product quality were the result. Continuous efforts and considerable energy were required to increase output. Despite the challenges of wartime, from 1943 onward—and especially after the region gained administrative independence—there were some improvements in using light and local industries for military needs. Investment in local industry increased sharply, which allowed the production of more goods in the Kashkadarya region.

The Bukhara shoe factory also shifted to producing goods for the military, fulfilling 115% of its semiannual plan.

A great patriotic initiative was launched by women working on the Kogon railway: on July 10, 1941, 100 women quickly trained to become technicians, turners, drillers,

communication workers, and station attendants, taking over positions left vacant by men who had gone to the front.

The number of workers at industrial enterprises in Bukhara increased due to housewives joining the workforce. Many women were quickly employed at factories.

Local industry enterprises produced more than 300 types of goods such as metalware, spoons, kitchen utensils, and cotton fabric, and sent them to the front. In the first half of 1941, local factories in Bukhara produced goods worth 1,893,300 soums. After five months of war, this figure increased to 2,577,500 soums.

On December 14, 1939, the League of Nations declared the USSR an aggressor and expelled it from the organization. In July 1940, the Red Army occupied Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia, imposing Soviet rule through force. On August 2, 1940, full Soviet control was established over Moldova, transforming the Moldavian ASSR into the Moldavian SSR. On August 5, Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia were forcibly incorporated into the Soviet Union.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the rural laborers of Uzbekistan made significant contributions to accelerating the victory over German fascism by working in extremely difficult and harsh conditions. During the war years, the republic's farmers supplied the front and victory efforts with critical resources: 4,148,000 tons of cotton, 82 million poods of grain, 57,444 tons of fruit and grapes, 36,000 tons of dried fruit, 159,300 tons of meat, 22.3 thousand tons of wool, and many other essential products. This is a tremendous and unparalleled feat of courage. We are justly and lawfully proud of it.

The war of 1941–1945 should serve as a historical lesson for us. Our people took into account all the hardships caused by the war and worked diligently and consciously on every front, demonstrating awareness and determination. However, our colonial masters regarded this work as a legal process and did not appreciate the efforts of the laboring class. This is evident in the post-war policies of Moscow, which, under the guise of great-power politics, pursued a path of specializing Uzbekistan's agriculture exclusively in cotton production. This led to an intensification of cotton monoculture.

Uzbekistan remained a raw material base for the USSR. This situation became a national tragedy for Uzbek workers and was the main cause of the political, economic, and spiritual impoverishment of the nation.

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